

Analysis of the drivers of practices in the irrigated farming systems: a multi-level spatial explicit approach in northern Tunisia during the past 15 years

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Abstract: The southern Mediterranean region displays remarkable diversity and heterogeneity, reflected in the dynamic mosaic of farms and farming systems that have evolved to adapt to the frequent scarcity and irregularity of water availability. Using the Echraf irrigated area in northern Tunisia as a case study, this paper addresses the decision-making process of farmers regarding crop choice and management practices. Drawing from 15 years of real land use data and interviews with experts from the local administration and farmers' associations, we identified the main cropping systems and analysed the determinants of farmers' decision-making, with a focus on tomato production system. The results highlight the nuanced influence of different factors on farmers' decision-making processes. The regional distribution of processing facilities underscores the broader decision-making dynamics and competitive pressures faced by farmers.

Keywords: Farming practices; Determinant factors; Cropping systems; Southern Mediterranean; Tunisia.

1. Purpose

Agricultural systems in the Mediterranean basin are expected to undergo rapid transitions over the next decade, as they appear to be more vulnerable to current changes, occurring at different scales and under various forms (Blondel, 2006; Cramer et al., 2018; Nieto-Romero et al., 2014). The latest IPCC report (2023, p. 48) identifies the Mediterranean agricultural systems among the most vulnerable to drought originated by climate change. However, in the Southern Mediterranean, the technical and financial capacities to implement large-scale adaptation measures are insufficient to cope with the problem (Djellouli-Tabet, 2010; Schilling et al., 2020). The high level of heterogeneity and complexity of these areas increases the farming system vulnerability, as it hampers the capacity of farmers to adapt their agricultural practices to the changes in the technical, social, and economic framework conditions (Ferchichi et al., 2020).

Several studies have focused on characterising the dynamics of cropping systems and interpreting the farmers' decision-making logic and systems in order to understand the adaptation of farming practices and how they can simultaneously address the challenges related to the environment, resource use efficiency and the economic sustainability of farms (Biarnès et al., 2021). Cropping system choices result from a decision-making process in which farmers weigh various objectives and constraints that are embedded in different spatial and temporal dynamics. Because production decisions are almost always made under uncertainty and multiple crops can follow within the same agricultural year, cropping system decision-making is a continuous process occurring throughout the year rather than a single simple choice (Dury et al., 2012). Explaining the coherence of the cropping system in relation to the objectives of the stakeholders, the constraints to which they are subject, and the existence of various interactions between techniques, is an essential step, both for assessing agricultural practices and for improving their economic or environmental efficiency.

Analyzing the spatio-temporal dynamics of cropping systems and their underlying drivers is especially challenging in the context of Southern Mediterranean systems for two main reasons: (1) the significant knowledge gap when it comes to characterizing and assessing the nature and causes of ongoing dynamics in the Southern Mediterranean systems (Debolini et al., 2018), and (2) the lack of available local and even generic datasets to track crop sequences and crop management practices, qualified as a major obstacle in describing dynamic cropping systems due to the high spatial and temporal heterogeneity of farmers' decision making (Rizzo et al., 2019). This study aims to describe farmers' decision-making process regarding crop choice and management practices, and to identify the determining factors of these decisions, based on 15 years of real data on land use occupation in the Echraf irrigated area, and on interviews with managers and technicians from agricultural public administration and farmers' association. This study case is a representative of irrigated farming systems in the northeastern part of Tunisia. It comprises small and scattered farms that are characterized by a high heterogeneity of crops, making it challenging to analyze cropping systems, particularly when it comes to understanding the dynamic distribution of crop sequences and their driving factors.

2. Material and Method

2.1. Case study

The Echraf public irrigation scheme is located on the Haouaria plain in Cap Bon and is administratively attached to the Nabeul governorate (Fig. 1). The cultivated area covers 305 ha and is irrigated from groundwater, from a collective irrigation network and from private and individual wells. The collective irrigation network is managed by the farmers' association called GDA Echraf.

Figure 1. Localisation of the study area of Echraf (Source: image SPOT6_2022_CHF-ORTHO)

The agricultural sector is managed by the regional administration (CRDA Nabeul) at the level of the Cap Bon region and by the CTV at the level of the Haouaria region. Farming systems are diversified: some are specialised in perennial crops (citrus, olive, etc), others in a mix of vegetables and fodder crops and others in livestock.

2.2. Method

For the study of the spatio-temporal distribution of cropping systems in the irrigated area of Echraf, we created a georeferenced database in 2018. This spatial database specifies for each farm, the location of their plots, its geometric shape and area and land use occupation, as well as its irrigation water resource. We gave each plot a unique identifier and attributes to describe its general characteristics (area, type of land tenure, etc.). Since then, this database has been updated for each season of the year. To create this database, we collected and spatialised different forms of data that the GDA generated from 2008 to 2017: (1) paper maps and plans (plot maps, land use maps, irrigation network plans, etc.) and (2) electronic datasheets containing data for each farm (cultivated area, irrigated area, seasonal water consumption, etc.). Using the spatial database, we were able to analyze the cropping systems and identify the most frequent crop sequences in the studied area. Data on the different crops and the evolution of their cultivated areas and production at the level of Haouaria region were also collected from various public agricultural administrations and its local offices to compare the territorial and the local dynamics of cropping systems distribution.

Between July and October 2023, face-to-face interviews were conducted with 11 managers from the CRDA, the CTV and the GDA. Interviewees were asked to: (1) identify the main crops in the area, (2) explain the determinant drivers for the choice of these crop types; (3) identify the three most important factors from the farmers' point of view and (4) describe the cropping calendar and management practices for each main crop. Maps of land use occupation from 2018 to 2023 were used during these interviews to facilitate the discussion on the cropping systems change in the Echraf area. These data were meant to help the interviewees remember events that may have affected the farmers' decisions. For the main crops, we retraced the agricultural practices, the farmers' decisional system and the actors that can affect these decisions for each crop.

In this paper, we are focusing on the determinants of farmers' decisions related to tomato crop production. Since 2010, the tomato area has decreased significantly, mainly due to water scarcity and the development of tomato production in other areas, leading to the increasing of farmers' vulnerability (Arfa and Elloumi, 2021). In order to better assess this vulnerability, we analysed the influence of different factors on farmers' decisions, particularly during the harvesting and selling of tomato crops.

3. Findings

Tomato is the second most frequent crop in the area; it is mainly cultivated in farms where the cultivated area exceeds 5 ha (large farms), located downstream of the irrigated area. In 2023, tomato was cultivated in 36% of the large farms. The conducted interviews revealed that the most important factors driving the farmers' choice of tomato crop are agro-economic, such as the selling price, the water security, the farmers' experience and mastery of agricultural practices, and the labour costs, regardless of the spatial level of analysis: the territory or the irrigated system.

We analysed in this paper the farmer's decision-making system during the harvesting and marketing phases of the tomato crop, when the farmer faces the greatest uncertainties, linked in particular to the socio-economic context of the region and to the climate. In this example, we consider a typical year where we have considered only the uncertainty related to the climatic conditions (temperature). The availability of irrigation water is not considered as a determinant factor because the farm water needs can easily be satisfied by the collective network of the GDA or the private wells.

For the tomato crop, the most frequent crop sequence in the study area is fodder crop/tomato/fodder crop. In this case, the farmer has to plant his tomatoes between the end of February and mid-June. If the selling price is attractive and the farmer wants to ensure the sale of his

production, he will sign in advance a contract with the tomato processing plant, specifying the choice of variety, the selling price and the quality required. Regardless of what happens (any hazardous events, climatic or financial, etc.), the farmer must honor this contract. In this paper, we refer to this decision system as DS1. If the farmer has chosen to go through a collection center, the date of harvest in this case depends mainly on the weather conditions (DS2). The collection center will proceed with the sale according to the date of harvest. If the temperature is mild, the crop can be harvested and sold on the market by the end of July. If the temperature is high, the farmer is obliged to harvest by the beginning of June at the latest, the production will be sold to tomato plants (DS3). Some farmers choose to sell directly to the market if farm labour is not available (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Decisional system-choice of tomato crop-Stage: Harvesting and selling (GICA-Union of Food Canning Industries; UTICA-Tunisian Union of Industry, Trade and Handicraft; UTAP-Tunisian Union Of Agriculture and Fisheries)

Several actors can directly or indirectly influence farmers' decisions. For example, even though the CRDA is more involved in controlling the areas of tomatoes irrigated by surface water than by groundwater, it can still indirectly influence farmers' decisions. When the CRDA restricts water-intensive cropping in public areas irrigated from the surface water, farmers in groundwater irrigation systems like Echraf, are encouraged to cultivate tomatoes. The UTAP is another example of an actor directly affecting farmers' decisions. A national committee to prepare and monitor the industrial sector is made up of representatives of GICA, UTICA and UTAP. At the start of each tomato growing season, this committee decides on the areas to be cultivated, based on the Tunisian market's requirements for canned tomato (the dominant processed form), export forecasts and the level of canned tomato stocks. This committee also sets the selling price of tomatoes to processing plants. UTAP's regional structure in Nabeul can influence the decisions of farmers in Echraf, by informing them in advance of possible increases in tomato selling prices, and restrictions imposed on other tomato-producing regions. For example, at the end of 2022, farmers were informed of the increase in the selling price for the summer of 2023. Between 2022 and 2023, the price of 1kg has risen from 230 millimes to 280 millimes (1 Tunisian dinar = 1000 millimes = 0,34 euro in 2023), the tomato cultivated area in the El Haouaria region has increased by 12% and has doubled in the Echraf system.

Another key actor is the industrial processor, which controls and coordinates the production chain for processed tomatoes and imposes its conditions on the farmers. The written contract between the producer and the processor helps to reduce price volatility, and UTAP plans to amend it to include more specific requirements, such as payment according to the quality. Figure 3 shows that farms in Nabeul produce 57% of the country's processed tomatoes from production areas that are not limited to Cap Bon but also include other regions such as Sidi-Bouzid, Beja and Kairouan. In 2022, 11 of the 17

factories operating in Tunisia are located in Cap Bon, making it the leading tomato processing area in the country (GICA, 2022). In the Echraf region, 4 factories are operating (Somocap, Socodal, Brima and STICA). During times of oversupply, farmers often consent to sell their yield at prevailing prices to avoid the risk of spoilage and unsellable produce.

Figure 3. (a) Localisation of industrial tomato processing areas, their contribution to national processing and flow of tomatoes transfers between producing areas and processing plants in 2022-(b) Illustrative diagram of potential directions of industrial tomato production in Echraf system (Producers in Echraf may sell their yield to (1) one of four local plants within the Echraf region or (2) to external plants (typically in Cap Bon and occasionally in distant areas). They compete with (3) other tomato producers from outside the Echraf region which can influence the selling price).

4. Practical implications

The results of this study present an example of a farmer's decision-making system concerning a structural crop, the industrial tomato. Through rapid interviews with managers at different scales (regional and local), we tried to identify the main factors and actors influencing farmers' decision-making in light of possible changes in the social and economic system. This work will make it possible to develop realistic scenarios for the evolution of cultivated landscapes and, secondly, to jointly develop sustainable agricultural production alternatives that take into account significant changes in the political and social context. These rules will be used to build models of cropping system plans based on real data on the spatio-temporal evolution of cropping systems over the last 15 years. The development of such a model will enable policymakers to assess landscape changes, formulate policy strategies and anticipate their long-term impacts.

5. Theoretical implications

Farmers' decision-making involves several nested levels at different temporal and spatial scales. The analysis of farming practices in the case of industrial crops revealed the complexity of interdependencies between multiple factors within and outside the decision unit. This study highlights the need for multidisciplinary research that considers actors' logic and the socio-economic system they operate in, based on a mosaic of interdependent theories to elucidate farmers' decision-making processes. In addition to analyzing farmers' rational choices in the face of biophysical change or resource dependence, it has become crucial to analyze farmers' decisions in situations where outcomes depend on the actions of other actors, considering strategic interactions and mutual incentives. These actors may be internal or external to the level being analysed and may influence farmers' decisions directly or indirectly. The study also highlights the importance of considering the influence of institutional actors, such as the regional farmers' association or the public administration, emphasizing their indirect but significant impact on farmers' decisions.

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